

Wheat Disease Detection Web App using Ultralytics YOLOv8

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ABSTRACT

Wheat diseases have a significant impact on global wheat production. These diseases are often not detected on time which causes major crop loss and economic damage. Some of these diseases spread rapidly, often leaving the whole field in ruin. Sometimes farmers mistake the diseases for a different one and implement the wrong cure or take incorrect precautionary measures. All these problems can be solved in one stroke using WheatCheck. This Wheat disease detection Web App is free to use and easily available online to all users. It accurately detects the disease in seconds using an image detection model called Ultralytics YOLOv8 and even provides the user with the causes, preventions, and remedies. The app uses a Kaggle dataset to train the model on common wheat diseases, including rusts, mites and blights. It uses Streamlit to convert the algorithm into an interactive web application. The integration of machine learning (ML) with intuitive web design ensures that the *WheatCheck* app can be widely adopted across various platforms. This tool holds the potential to revolutionize wheat farming practices and significantly reduce crop losses due to disease.

Keywords: *WheatCheck, Ultralytics YOLOv8, Wheat diseases, Machine Learning, agriculture, Object Detection, Food Security, AI in agriculture*

1.INTRODUCTION

Wheat is a critical source of nutrients and calories for billions of people worldwide. However, a large amount of wheat crop is destroyed by diseases. This is not only disastrous for farmers, but also causes immense loss in essential resources like land, water and capital. Due to rising population and diminishing land holdings, there is an urgent need to revolutionize agriculture and make it more sustainable and efficient. Traditional approaches relying on manual inspection are not only time-consuming, but can also lead to inaccuracies, underscoring the need for technological advancements in disease detection.

This research aims to bridge that gap by leveraging advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), particularly in real-time object detection, to create a web-based tool for wheat disease detection. The *WheatCheck* app, built using Ultralytics YOLOv8 model, instantaneously detects wheat diseases by image analyses and presents farmers with causes, preventions, and remedies for the disease. *WheatCheck* uses a simple web interface, therefore providing a scalable solution to a broad audience.

Impact of Wheat on Food Security

Wheat is the most widely cultivated cereal crop globally, accounting for 220 million hectares of cultivated land and providing 20% of the world's dietary calories and proteins. Its nutritional value, comprising about 70% starch and 14% protein, makes it a staple food for 40% of the global population. Due to its significance, wheat is at the core of global food security, particularly in regions where it is a primary

food source. The demand for wheat has doubled since the 1980s, and developing countries now account for half of the global wheat production (Braun et al., 2010).

In India, wheat plays a critical role in the agricultural economy, with the country ranking as the second-largest wheat producer globally. Punjab plays a critical role in India's wheat production, contributing 19.5% of the total output. Despite this significant contribution, the state, and India as a whole, face challenges in terms of productivity. These issues stem from factors like declining soil fertility, overuse of pesticides and fertilizers, and a rapidly falling water table, which is crucial for agriculture in the region (PSC Exams, n.d.). India's cereal yields remain lower than in developed regions such as North America and Europe due to outdated agricultural practices, climate change, and pest infestations.

Impact of Wheat Diseases on Production and Economy

Wheat crops are vulnerable to various diseases, particularly fungal pathogens that thrive in changing climatic conditions. Wheat diseases, including rusts, mildews, and blights, can lead to devastating losses in global wheat production. These diseases account for significant yield reductions, often estimated at around 30% globally, resulting in the loss of millions of tonnes of wheat annually, which could amount to billions of dollars in economic damage. The global value of wheat lost to these diseases is estimated to be around \$31 billion each year (He et al., 2022; Jaggi & Sahgal, 2021)

These losses have severe implications for food security, as the calories wasted could feed up to 583 million people. Additionally, the resources required to cultivate diseased wheat crops, such as land, water, and fertilizers, are substantial.

Wheat-based raw materials, such as wheat starch and wheat proteins, are essential for modern food production. Bread and baked goods cover 20% of our daily calorie consumption and contribute significantly to a balanced diet. (Translator, 2020)

Wheat is the most widely cultivated cereal in the world, a staple food for 40 percent of the world's population that contributes 20 percent of total dietary calories and proteins worldwide (Braun et al., 2010). Wheat demand has doubled since the 1980s, with most of the demand coming from developing countries, which harvest 50 percent of global wheat production annually. Consequently, wheat is at the epicenter of global food security (Acevedo et al., 2018)

Challenges in Manual Detection of Wheat Diseases

Wheat diseases are complex and have a large variety, hence they are very difficult to detect manually. Visual examination has traditionally been the primary diagnostic technique during wheat cultivation. However, this method is becoming increasingly challenging as it demands significant time and effort from both farmers and pathologists to accurately measure infection levels. Manual detection of wheat diseases is not only time-intensive, labor-intensive, and resource-intensive, but also requires expert knowledge, often leading to poor performance and incorrect diagnoses.(Jouini et al., 2024)

Manual detection can also be prone to errors based on the inexperience of the identifier. Imagine the effort of passing this knowledge from one generation to another with new and more complex diseases being detected in rural and remote locations. Even the delay in finding the correct cure leads to a loss which usually always affects the yields of the crop.

If persons with zero knowledge can be guided through the process of accurate identification and the precise latest remedies available with detailed instructions on how to proceed, it would lead to a drastic reduction in anxiety amongst the farmer community. New remedies would also be adopted faster by the widespread farmer community.

Role of AI and Computer Vision in agriculture

Use of AI and computer aided tools have started to focus on solutions for agriculture. Accurate and quick identification of a disease followed by the correct remedies for cure can improve the Wheat productivity drastically. Hence, there is an increasing need for an automated, real-time detection system that offers farmers quick, actionable insights. AI intervention and using updated technology will not only improve the speed of detection but also the accuracy drastically, usually having a 98% accuracy, leading to substantial improvements in productivity.

With the growing population pressure on land these interventions will lead to superior accuracy and jumps in productivity in agriculture. Monarch Tractor is one such example using cutting edge interventions to get Tesla like solutions to agriculture. Utilizing AI-driven solutions for precise farm operations Monarch has launched the first smart, fully electric, self-driving tractor capable of scheduling and working for longer hours with minimal human interventions. Technocrats like James Dyson are promoting the transformative potential of AI. Computer aided vision along with robotics have the potential to transform agriculture contributing to highly efficient food production systems that can meet the demands of a growing population while reducing emissions and mitigating the environmental pressures.

While the above interventions are capital cost intensive, WheatCheck has a low cost but potential of a very high return. It is made using real-time AI-powered image analysis tools for disease detection. Through object detection models like YOLOv8, AI can analyze images of crops and detect diseases with remarkable speed and accuracy. With the ability to process images in real-time, AI-powered tools like WheatCheck are scalable, making them accessible to a broader population. This technology eliminates the need for time-consuming manual inspections and allows for large-scale disease detection. It has an interactive web interface which is easily usable on a smartphone device with options of multiple regional languages, especially necessary for a country like India with over 100 different languages.

Real time detection - Ultralytics YOLO v8

Yolov8 is a real time detection software imported in my code that helps detect the diseases in real time using the train and test data. YOLO (You Only Look Once) is a model that uses ML (machine learning) algorithms and CNNs (Computational Neural Networks) to detect objects. YOLOv8 is the newest state-of-the-art YOLO model that can be used for object detection, image classification, and instance segmentation tasks.

Figure 1: YOLOv8 real time object detection

WheatCheck imports Ultralytics and uses the YOLOv8 model to train and test data. YOLOv8 is an evolution in the YOLO (You Only Look Once) series of real time detection models. YOLOv8 comes pre-trained on large datasets like COCO (Common Objects in Context), allowing it to detect a wide variety of objects with high accuracy out of the box. The model can be fine-tuned for specific tasks or customized for specialized datasets. YOLO achieves its speed and efficiency by processing the entire image in a single forward pass through the neural network, unlike traditional models that require multiple passes. Its versatility makes it popular for applications like autonomous driving, surveillance, and robotics.

(a)

Figure 2: (a) Training data on the kaggle dataset

(b)

(b) Testing the model on the same kaggle dataset

In figure 2 (a) the model is getting trained on the training data in the Kaggle dataset. In figure 2 (b) the model is testing its accuracy on the testing data on the same dataset.

2.METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim

The aim of this project is to develop a web application that accurately detects and diagnoses common wheat diseases through image analysis. This application will utilize machine learning algorithms to analyze images of wheat crops, identify disease symptoms, and provide farmers with actionable insights to manage and mitigate these diseases effectively.

2.2 Data Collection

Image Dataset - Collect images of wheat crops affected by various diseases such as aphids, brown rust, mites, stem fly, black rust, common root rot, leaf blight, septoria, tan spot, blast, fusarium head blight, mildew, smut, and yellow rust. Sources for images for our data is kaggle ([wheat-plant-diseases](#))

2.3 App Development

Backend Development - Developed the backend using a github repository ([Harchet13/WheatDiseaseDetection](#)), which will handle the model inference and serve the web application.

Frontend Development - Built a user-friendly frontend using Streamlit ([/](#)). The interface is designed to allow users to upload images, view analysis, and receive detailed disease management advice.

2.4 Deployment

Deployed the web app on a Streamlit community cloud for scalability and reliability. Ensuring the application is secure, responsive, and accessible across different devices.

2.5 App and Data Collection

Figure 3: Implementation workflow of the WebApp

By integrating advanced machine learning techniques with an intuitive web interface, this wheat disease detection app aims to provide farmers with a powerful tool to maintain crop health, improve yields, and reduce the reliance on expert consultations.

Results

Figure 4: Confusion matrix taken for 50 images.

Figure 4 depicts a confusion matrix taken for 50 images in each disease. It shows the accuracy of the data. The horizontal (x-axis) shows the diseases actually affecting the diseased plant. The vertical axis (y-axis) represents the diseases predicted by WheatCheck. For example all 50 images which were taken for the aphid disease predicted the correct disease but two images that were actually Leaf Blight and Mite were predicted by as Aphid by the model.

Figure 5: Normalized confusion matrix

The above graph has been scaled to probability out of 1. That means that if the diseased crop has been infected by Aphids there is a probability of 1 (or 100%) that the disease will be predicted correctly. On the other hand there is a 2/100 chance that a plant diseased with leaf blight is predicted as Aphid.

epoch	train/loss	metrics/accuracy_top1	metrics/accuracy_top5	val/loss	lr/pg0	lr/pg1	lr/pg2
1	1.5021	0.712	0.97333	2.2166	0.00023742	0.00023742	0.00023742
2	0.66048	0.75067	0.96	2.1242	0.00045189	0.00045189	0.00045189
3	0.61618	0.764	0.96133	2.0907	0.00064279	0.00064279	0.00064279
4	0.55944	0.78667	0.94667	2.07	0.00060797	0.00060797	0.00060797
5	0.47815	0.8	0.98667	2.0566	0.00057263	0.00057263	0.00057263
6	0.40663	0.83467	0.99467	2.0242	0.00053728	0.00053728	0.00053728
7	0.35292	0.84267	0.99467	2.0053	0.00050194	0.00050194	0.00050194
8	0.3032	0.83467	0.96267	1.9993	0.0004666	0.0004666	0.0004666
9	0.27153	0.86533	0.99467	1.9702	0.00043126	0.00043126	0.00043126
10	0.24073	0.884	0.97867	1.9574	0.00039591	0.00039591	0.00039591
11	0.21672	0.87867	0.98267	1.9535	0.00036057	0.00036057	0.00036057
12	0.19691	0.91067	0.98667	1.9341	0.00032523	0.00032523	0.00032523
13	0.17115	0.88933	0.992	1.9326	0.00028988	0.00028988	0.00028988
14	0.1636	0.88667	0.99733	1.936	0.00025454	0.00025454	0.00025454
15	0.14569	0.89867	0.99467	1.9247	0.0002192	0.0002192	0.0002192
16	0.1272	0.916	0.99733	1.9126	0.00018385	0.00018385	0.00018385
17	0.11984	0.904	0.99333	1.9203	0.00014851	0.00014851	0.00014851
18	0.108	0.904	0.996	1.9176	0.00011317	0.00011317	0.00011317
19	0.09708	0.90133	0.996	1.9149	7.7826e-05	7.7826e-05	7.7826e-05
20	0.0913	0.90667	0.99733	1.9106	4.2483e-05	4.2483e-05	4.2483e-05

Figure 6: Accuracy of the trained data

This image gives more insight into the accuracy of the trained data. The data is trained by the network multiple times for it to be accurate. If the entire data consisting of 14,000+ images in this case is trained once, it is called an epoch. After all the data has been trained 20 times the algorithm has achieved an accuracy of 99.7% .

Figure 7: Some inferences from the data - loss vs epoch graphs

The above two graphs are loss vs epoch graphs. The first one is the training loss. Second one validation loss. Loss measures the error in the predicted class probabilities for each object in the image compared to the ground truth. A lower loss means that the model is more accurately predicting the class of the objects.

Bottom 2 are accuracy vs epoch graphs. Top 1 is the accuracy for predicting the most probable class. Top 5 is the accuracy of predicting the top 5 probable classes.

2.6 User Interface

The web interface is very user friendly. It contains all the information you require to use the application in distinct steps. It also has images for clarity and correlation. Separate user interfaces for computer and mobile were created.

3.DISCUSSION

The results of the experiment testify to the effectiveness of Ultralytics YOLOv8 for detecting wheat diseases. WheatCheck can achieve impressive accuracy because of comprehensive training on a really wide diversity of the dataset. The confusion matrix elicited in the course of testing attests that YOLOv8 can demonstrate really high capability for distinguishing between various wheat diseases. This ability is indispensable for real applications focused on agriculture. Misdiagnosis can lead to very serious consequences such as crop damage and unnecessary application of chemical treatments that make farming more complex in terms of sustainability.

Results of this study are in line with the growing body of literature informing on the application of AI and ML in the recognition of agricultural diseases. Many researches carried out by Mohanty et al. (2016) and Ferentinos (2018) have proven that AI-based methods greatly enhance both speed and accuracy in disease detection compared to traditional visual inspection methods. The WheatCheck application has the provision for farm usage diagnostics through a pre-trained YOLOv8 model tailored for wheat diseases; therefore, actions to intervene timely can be undertaken before losses are incurred in crops.

The tremendous scalability of the WheatCheck app demonstrates its ability to shift agricultural scope. Its detection capability does not depend on the limited human input and skill possessed by most surveyor inspection methods. With the help of AI-driven detection, huge expanses of agriculture can be inspected along with results achieved in real time. Moreover, cloud services make this app even more accessible. Through this technology, farmers, even located remotely, can now send their samples through the internet for analysis (Hannah et al., 2019). This feature could also be very useful when applied to developing countries that often find resources limited.

However, limitations of this study must be acknowledged. The quality and quantity of the training data determine the accuracy of the YOLOv8 model. Although the Kaggle dataset used in this research contains a solid representation of common wheat diseases, there may be rare infrequent diseases or subtle visual symptoms for which a picture has not been included and results in detection gaps (Kumar et al., 2020). Beyond that, the requirement of internet and suitable mobile devices would further narrow the scale of utility of the WheatCheck tool in some agricultural communities, more so in developing economies where digital infrastructure is still being developed (Börner et al., 2021).

Despite these challenges, the results showed that AI-based technologies such as WheatCheck may have great potential in the contributions they may give toward reducing losses in crops due to diseases and hence increasing food security, which should subsequently also spur sustainable agriculture. Research in the future

should include expanding the dataset to the spectrum of wheat diseases, extending the access of the app when connectivity is not well developed in a particular region, and then reshaping the model for other crops and the agricultural sectors.

4.CONCLUSION

The research highlights the efficacy of using ML and image detection models like Ultralytics YOLOv8 to make many agricultural processes more efficient. WheatCheck offers farmers a tool to reduce the manual burden of disease identification, leading to improved crop yields and economic savings. The confusion matrix and graphs show that the pre-trained model has high accuracy of detection and thus can be trusted by farmers across the globe. The web interface is easy to use and multilingual allowing it to serve a large number of people. The dataset has a substantial range of common diseases. Collaboration with local authorities could enhance the application's accessibility and practicality. The application has already been recognised by the Government of India and received recommendations from Shri Shivraj Singh Chouhan, Hon'ble Minister of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare; Maharaja Amrinder Singh, former Chief Minister and Agriculture Minister of Punjab; and Shri Ganesh Joshi, Agriculture Minister of Uttarakhand.

Limitations:

Despite its successful characteristics, WheatCheck is limited by the quality and diversity of the training dataset. The model's accuracy may decrease when applied to less common diseases or variations not represented in the dataset. Internet access and device availability may pose challenges in some rural areas. The model is also pre-trained which may hinder the performance due to different locations and limited customisation. There may be a bias due to pre-existing data. It also currently has only 3 different languages- English, Hindi, and Punjabi- which poses a difficulty in places like Europe and Africa. High illiteracy rates in many locations in India may pose a challenge.

Future Implications:

The WheatCheck app has the potential to significantly impact global agriculture by reducing the need for expert consultations and enabling farmers to act quickly against crop diseases. In the future the data produced by the usage of the app could be collected and used to predict the most common diseases and their locations, so that a conscientious effort can be made to eradicate them. The number of languages can be increased to increase the reach of the application. A feedback loop could be added, where the image of the diseased crop taken and approved by the user can be added to the database to increase the number of images in the database and thus, further increase the accuracy. A widget can be added that can transport the application to the home screen, so that users won't have to open the link every time to use the app. Finally a voice-over can be added to help interaction with users who are illiterate. Youtube links could be provided for furthering the understanding of the disease and the suggested measures. Expansion of the software to detect diseases of other crops is planned for the future. Professors and researchers can be allowed to input their additions in the causes, preventions and cures to further improve the advisory. Further improvements in AI, cloud computing,

and mobile accessibility can extend this tool to other regions and crops, supporting global food security efforts and mitigating the effects of climate change on agriculture.

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